

Folklore Examples In Komil Sindarov's "The Investigator: Adventures In Exile"

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Abstract

This article analyzes the use of folklore, particularly proverbs, in the work "The Investigator: Adventures in Exile" by Komil Sindarov, a lawyer, associate professor, and author of dozens of books. The article explores the role of proverbs in enhancing the artistic value of the work.

Keywords: folklore, proverb, term, oral folklore, fairy tale, anecdote, genre, proverb, paremiology, theme, image, literal meaning, figurative meaning, contrast, artistic technique, plot.

INTRODUCTION

Komil Sindarov was born on November 27, 1960, in the Qo'shrabod district of Samarkand region. He began his career at Samarkand State University named after Sharof Rashidov, holding various responsible positions. Komil Sindarov has authored dozens of literary and detective works, including stories like "The Expensive Mistake," "Murder on the Night of Dignity," "Delayed Revenge," and "Night Murder," which have been warmly received by the general public and critics.

This article analyzes the proverbs, a folklore example, used in his detective story "The Investigator: Adventures in Exile." The term "folklore" is derived from the words "folk" and "lore," meaning "folk wisdom." The term "folklore" was first used by William Toms in 1846, and in Uzbek literature, it was first introduced by H. Zarif in 1934-35. Before that, it was known as "folk literature," "people's literature," and "oral literature."

The creator of folklore is the people; it is a collective creation. The folklorist scholar Okhunjon Safarov, in his book "Uzbek Folk Oral Creativity," stated that the basis of folklore is its popular nature

– its advanced ideological nature. In folklore works, language is paramount, particularly in fairy tales, legends, anecdotes, jokes, riddles, and proverbs. Anonymity, variability, versification, traditionality, and orality are the distinctive characteristics of folklore.

The genre of proverbs, belonging to a specific type of folklore, is widely used not only in oral literature but also in written literature by our writers and poets. The word "proverb" comes from the Arabic word "quvvala," meaning "to say," "to speak." The writer Komil Sindarov has used over 60 examples of proverbs in his story "The Investigator: Adventures in Exile." The work serves to raise the legal awareness and culture of a wide readership – the population. The proverbs used in the work enhance its popular nature and artistic impact.

Folklorists say that paremiology is the field that studies proverbs; this word comes from the Greek meaning "deeply meaningful speech," "wise words." As mentioned above, the approximately 60 proverbs used in "Adventures in Exile" cover diverse thematic areas. Scientific literature notes that proverbs are spoken on about 30 themes. This

once again demonstrates the wisdom of our people. The book "Anthology of Uzbek Folk Oral Creativity" by T. Mirzayev, O. Safarov, and D. Jo'rayeva provides examples of proverbs on themes such as homeland, patriotism, friendship, harmony, knowledge, ignorance, wisdom, thrift, vigilance, goodness, honesty, courage, love, luck, beauty, knowledge, cowardice, love, loyalty, family, and neighborhood.

The proverbs used in the work, such as "My empty stomach – my peaceful ears" (page 5), "A student who has not surpassed the teacher is not a student" (page 21), "You've fallen into the letter – you've fallen into the fire" (page 26), "The name of fear is cowardice" (page 37), "A necessary stone has no weight" (page 61), "While the thinker's thought is complete, the gambler's work is done" (page 75), "His body knows no other pain" (page 101), "His name is great – his table is empty" (page 102), "If there is no wind, the tree's top will not move" (page 156), "Two fifteen, one thirty" (page 181), "Don't play with the boss, the boss will punish you with every chapter" (page 247), "What came in with blood will go out with life" (page 247), cover diverse thematic areas. The proverbs reveal the events in the story, the characters' actions, and the heroes' intellectual abilities and high level of understanding. This is because the main characters of the story – Mirzo Okhunovich, Sanjarbek Rahmonov, Tohir G'ofurovich, Bahrom, and Jo'raboy Xolmurod aka – use proverbs appropriately and with deep reflection, based on the situation, plot, and composition of the work.

Proverbs in Komil Sindarov's "The Investigator: Adventures in Exile". Proverbs can have both literal and figurative meanings. In the story, the characters use proverbs like "The dog lies down, the gentleman stands up" (page 5), "Don't brag, goose, your skill is small" (page 21), "Dog's skill, the caravan passes" (page 30), "The calf's run reaches the hayloft" (page 31), "One cannot escape a rabbit

for long" (page 43), "Too much talk is a burden on a camel" (page 75), "He may fall from the horse, but not from the saddle" (page 85), and "A bird knows the language of a bird" (page 301). These proverbs are all examples of figurative language. Proverbs are considered to be rare examples of folk wisdom. They often use artistic language devices, especially stylistic and spiritual techniques, particularly antithesis. In the story, proverbs such as "Under the heavy, over the light" (page 6), "Great name, dry soup" (page 102), and "If he knows, it's a joke, if he doesn't, it's true" (page 183) effectively use the technique of antithesis. Antithesis is the art of using words or phrases that express opposing ideas.

In the late 1980s, the staff of the Alisher Navoiy Institute of Language and Literature of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan published about 13,000 proverbs in alphabetical order. The Hungarian orientalist Hermann Vámbéry included 112 Uzbek proverbs in Arabic and Latin scripts in the chrestomathy part of his "Textbook of the Chagatai Language," published in Leipzig in 1867, and translated them into German. Many other Uzbek writers and poets have also used proverbs effectively in their works.

In conclusion, proverbs are a high form of word art that has been actively used in both old and young speech since ancient times. Proverbs can be used at work, in casual or serious discussions, and in events. Using a proverb in every sentence strengthens the impact of speech or a work by confirming and substantiating the idea. The proverbs used in Komil Sindarov's "The Investigator: Adventures in Exile" enhance the author's artistic thinking, the essence and content of the work, its artistic value, and its folk character.

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